

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		26-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Hu et al.	
Affiliation(s)		China	
Publication year		2021	
Title of article		Effects of a WeChat-based individualized post-discharge rehabilitation program on patients with lumbar fusion surgery	
Title of journal		Journal of Back and Musculoskeletal Rehabilitation	
Volume 35	Issue 5	Pages 1-13	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify): Quasi-experimental design	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Participants	The patients discharged after LFS from the Spinal Surgery Department of the First People Hospital of Nantong, China. Lumbar fusion surgery with no prior history of spinal surgery	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of intervention	A 10-week WeChat-based individualized rehabilitation program	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract, Figure 1, p. 8, p. 11
Types of comparison	Routine follow-up guidance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3

Types of outcome measures	Pain, function disability /status, patients' compliance, exercise self-efficacy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 3, 6
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	This study aimed to evaluate the formulation and implementation of an effective WeChat-based individualized post-discharge rehabilitation program for LFS patients with the participation of clinicians, rehabilitation therapists, and clinical nurses.	p. 2
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Quasi-experimental design	p. 2
Start date	October 2018	p. 2
End date	Februar 2019	p. 2
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear This study was approved and supported by the school of nursing of Nantong University and the Spinal Surgery Department of the First People Hospital of Nantong, China, and was registered under trial registration number CTR2000033947.	p. 6

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Spinal Surgery Department	p. 2
Inclusion criteria	(1) underwent LFS with no prior history of spinal surgery; (2) received routine nursing care in the spinal surgery department of the hospital as per surgeon's discharge instructions; (3) were able to use smart phones and the WeChat app; and (4) were over 18 years of age and willing to cooperate in the data collection.	p. 2

Exclusion criteria	The exclusion criteria were: (1) pregnancy; (2) serious organ diseases such as that of liver, lung, and brain; (3) inability to exercise due to musculoskeletal disorders or limb and joint deformities; and (4) readmission or reoperation due to disease progression or improper treatment.	p. 2
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes No Unclear	p. 6

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Experimental group	p. 3, 6, 9, 10, 11
No. of participants	36	p. 7 table 2
Mean age	57.6	p. 7 table 2
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	<p>Type:</p> <p>A 10-week WeChat-based individualized rehabilitation program.</p> <p>Content:</p> <p>Individualized post-discharge rehabilitation program, including exercise types, number of sessions in a day, repetitions of each exercise in a session, duration of each session and precautions. The researchers educated the patients and their family members about lumbar fusion surgery, the possibility of fluctuations in the pain and recurrence of the original disease, clinical manifestations of a worsening condition, and the corresponding countermeasures to be taken. The researcher also informed the patients about the importance of rehabilitation after lumbar fusion surgery, and asked family members to help the patients to participate in the rehabilitation program, and maintain a positive lifestyle. The patients in the experimental group were invited to join the WeChat group named as ‘Post-discharge Rehabilitation Management for Patients with Lumbar Fusion Surgery’. The rehabilitation of the experimental group was conducted via WeChat. Group meetings were held every fortnight, where the researcher informed the team of problems and issues raised by the patient during the intervention. Solutions were discussed and recorded during the meetings and these solutions were communicated to the patient through WeChat the next day.</p>	p. 3

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group	p. 7 table 2
No. of participants	36	p. 7 table 2
Mean age	62.3	p. 7 table 2
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Routine follow-up guidance: On the day before the discharge, the researchers communicated the routine discharge instructions to the patients and followed-up by telephone in the first, second, and third months after the surgery. The instructions at the time of follow-up included those pertaining to exercise rehabilitation, medication schedule, and lumbar brace wearing/unloading.	Abstract, p. 3

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain	Abstract, p. 3, 9
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Numerical Rating Scale (NRS)	Abstract, p. 3, 9

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Function disability /status	Abstract, p. 3, 9
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Oswestry Disability Index (ODI)	Abstract, p. 3, 9

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Patients' compliance	Abstract, p. 3, 6, 8, 9, 10
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Exercise Compliance Questionnaire	Abstract, p. 3, 6, 8, 9, 10

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Exercise self-efficacy	Abstract, p. 3, 8, 9, 10, 11
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	The Chinese version of the self-efficacy for exercise scale (SEE-C)	Abstract, p. 3, 8, 9, 10, 11

Follow-up

Follow up	3 months	p. 3
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Results: The analysis using generalized estimation equations method shows significant differences in the interaction effect of group*time in exercise compliance (Wald c 2 = 7.459, P < 0.05), group effect in pain (Wald c 2 = 5.811, P < 0.05) and self-efficacy (Wald c 2 = 16.383, P < 0.05). However, there was no significant difference between the experimental and control groups in the group effect in dysfunction improvement (Wald c 2 = 2.289, P > 0.05).</p> <p>Conclusions: The WeChat-based rehabilitation intervention can improve exercise compliance and self-efficacy, and help achieve greater pain relief compared to the routine intervention. However, the WeChat-based intervention did not offer better improvement in the self-dysfunction in the post-discharge LFS patients.</p>	Abstract, p. 11

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>